

INDO AMERICAN JOURNAL OF PHARMACEUTICAL RESEARCH

FORMULATION AND IN VITRO EVALUATION OF HUMECTANT MUCOADHESIVE BUCCAL TABLETS

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ARTICLE INFO

Article history

Received 27/07/2019

Available online
31/08/2019

Keywords

Sumatriptan Succinate,
Mucoadhesion,
HPMC K4M,
Guar gum,
Ethyl cellulose,
Migraine.

ABSTRACT

The objective of present studies was to develop a Sumatriptan succinate buccal mucoadhesive tablet using mucoadhesive polymers such as HPMC K4M, ethyl cellulose and guar gum in alone and in combination as release retarding agent to prolong the drug release, to increase mucoadhesive strength and to avoid first pass metabolism. The mucoadhesive buccal tablets were prepared by wet granulation method. The prepared granules of all the formulations were evaluated for precompression parameters to ensure flow properties during tablet punching. The prepared mucoadhesive buccal tablets were evaluated for physicochemical parameters such as hardness, thickness uniformity, weight variation, and moisture absorption studies. The prepared buccal tablets were also evaluated for mucoadhesive strength and *in vitro* drug release dissolution studies. The drug excipients compatibility was evaluated by FTIR and DSC studies. *Ex vivo* mucoadhesive strength, and *in vitro* release studies showed that formulation SMF₆ containing all the three polymers combination showed satisfactory bioadhesive and exhibited optimum drug release (99.33 % after 10hrs). FTIR and DSC results showed no evidence of interaction between the Sumatriptan succinate and mucoadhesive polymers. Hence different mucoadhesive polymers (HPMC K4M, ethyl cellulose and guar gum) in various proportions can be used to prepare mucoadhesive buccal tablets of Sumatriptan succinate having prolonged therapeutic effect with enhanced patient compliance by avoiding first pass metabolism.

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Please cite this article in press as **Safoora Naaz et al.** Formulation And in Vitro Evaluation of Humectant Mucoadhesive Buccal Tablets. *Indo American Journal of Pharmaceutical Research*.2019;9(08).

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INTRODUCTION

Oral drug administration is the preferred and most common route for drug delivery. Several advantages associated with it include: it is patient-friendly, pain less, has the ease of self-medication, and allows for a flexible and controlled dosing schedule in comparison to most other drug delivery systems. Although the oral route is preferred for administration of drugs, it also presents major disadvantages such as first pass effect, gastrointestinal enzymatic degradation and delay between the time of administration and absorption, which is detrimental in the case of drugs with rapid onset requirements. These difficulties have provided the impetus for exploring alternative routes for the delivery of drugs, which include routes such as pulmonary, ocular, nasal, rectal, buccal, sublingual, vaginal, and transdermal. Transmucosal routes of drug delivery which is comprised of the mucosal linings of the nasal, rectal, vaginal, ocular, and oral cavity offer excellent opportunities and potential advantages over per oral administration for systemic drug delivery.

These advantages include possible bypass of first pass effect, avoidance of presystemic elimination within the GI tract and, depending on the particular drug, a better enzymatic flora for drug absorption. Within the oral mucosal cavity, delivery of drugs is broadly classified into two categories: (a) sublingual delivery, which is systemic delivery of drugs through the mucosal membranes lining the floor of the mouth and (b) buccal delivery, which is drug administration through mucosal membranes lining the cheeks (buccal mucosa).

THE IMPORTANT OBJECTIVES OF THE PROPOSED RESEARCH WORK:

- 1) To carry out pre formulation studies on drug and polymer(s) and to establish their compatibility in formulation using methods like TLC.
- 2) To formulate Mucoadhesive buccal tablets using varying concentrations of Sumatriptan (drug) and polymers like Carbopol 934p, HPMC K4M, Ethyl cellulose, Guar gum. The Mucoadhesive buccal tablets will be prepared by direct compression method.
- 3) To study the effect of various factors like Polymer to drug ratio, polymer ratio on the response parameters like release rate, bio adhesive strength and in vitro drug release.
- 4) To study the release pattern and to conclude the mechanism of release and release rate kinetics.

PLAN OF THE RESEARCH WORK:

- Design of the muco adhesive buccal tablets.
- Evaluation of these designed formulations for the response parameters (T_{0.5}, Release rates and Bio adhesive strength).
- Evaluation of these formulations for In-vitro mucoadhesion, Assay of drug content, content uniformity, swelling studies.
- Study *In-vitro* release kinetics of the formulations.
- To carry out accelerated stability studies on the muco adhesive buccal formulations.

METHODOLOGY

INSTRUMENTS USED

S.NO	INSTRUMENTS	COMPANY MADE
1	Hardness tester	Monsanto hardness tester
2	Digital balance	KEROY electronic precision balance
3	Friability test apparatus	Roche friabilitor
4	Tablet dissolution tester	Lab India DS800
5	Bulk density apparatus	SECOR, India
6	Digital pH meter	Systronics type -362, Noble Enterprises.
7	UV visible spectrophotometer	Analytical technology 2040
8	Multi station rotary punch (tablet compression machine)	Saimach ,pharmatechpvtltd,tablet press lab -10
9	FTIR spectrophotometer	Shimadzu
10	DSC	Pyris Diamond TG/DTA

Materials Used

S.NO	MATERIALS	COMPANY MADE
1	Sumatriptan succinate	Dr.Reddy lab , Hyd
2	HPMC K4M	Dr.Reddy lab , Hyd
3	Carbopol 934P	S.D Fine Chemicals
4	Ethyl cellulose	S.D.Fine Chemicals
5	Guar gum	Dr.Reddy lab , Hyd
6	Pvk k30	S.D. Fine Chemicals
7	Lactose	S.D. Fine Chemicals
8	Magnesium stearate	S.D Fine Chemicals
9	Talc & titanium dioxide	S.D Fine Chemicals

ESTIMATION OF SUMATRIPTAN SUCCINATE:

Determination of λ_{\max} of sumatriptan succinate in distilled water:

Weighed amount of sumatriptan dissolved in distilled water to obtain a 1000 mcg/ml solution. This solution was subjected to scanning between 200-400 nm and absorption maximum was determined. The effect of dilution on absorption maxima was studied by diluting the above solution to 10 mcg/ml and scanned from 200-400 nm. From the spectra of drug max of sumatriptan succinate 220 nm was selected for the analysis. The calibration curve was prepared in the concentration range of 1-6 mcg/ml at 220 nm. By using the calibration curve, the concentration of the sample solution can be determined.

Standard calibration curve of sumatriptan succinate in distilled water:

STANDARD STOCK SOLUTION: A stock solution containing 1 mg/ml of pure drug was prepared by dissolving 100 mg of sumatriptan in sufficient distilled water to produce 100 ml solution in a volumetric flask.

STOCK SOLUTION: From the standard stock solution, 5 ml of the stock solution was further diluted to 50 ml with distilled water into a 50 ml volumetric flask and diluted up to the mark with distilled water. Aliquots of 1, 2, 3, 4, and 5 ml of stock solution were pipetted out into 10ml volumetric flasks. The volume was made up to the mark with distilled water. These dilutions give 1, 2, 3, 4 and 5 mcg/ml concentration of sumatriptan succinate respectively. The absorbance was measured in the UV- Visible spectrophotometer at 220nm using distilled water as blank and graph of concentration versus absorbance was plotted.

Absorbance values to corresponding concentration for standard calibration curve of Sumatriptan succinate P^H 6.8.

Sl. No	CONCENTRATION	ABSORBANCE
1	0	0.000
2	1	0.114
3	2	0.197
4	3	0.292
5	4	0.389
6	5	0.490

Chart 3.1 Standard calibration curve of Sumatriptan in Phosphate buffer P^H 6.8

The linear regression analysis for the calibration curve:

The linear regression analysis was done on absorbance data points. The results are as follows:

Slope (m) = 0.096

Intercept (c) = 0.004

Correlation coefficient (R^2) = 0.998

A straight line equation ($y = mx + c$) was generated to facilitate the calculation for amount of drug. The equation is as follows

$$\text{Absorbance (y)} = 0.096 \times \text{concentration (x)} + 0.006 \text{ (c)}$$

Different formulations of Sumatriptan Succinate buccal mucoadhesive tablets.

Formulations (mg)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆
Sumatriptan	10	10	10	10	10	10
HPMC K4M	25	25	30	35	30	20
Ethyl cellulose	20	-	15	-	-	15
Guar gum	-	20	-	10	15	10
Lactose	74.5	74.5	74.5	74.5	74.5	74.5
PVP K30	15	15	15	15	15	15
Mg stearate	3	3	3	3	3	3
Talc	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5	1.5
Saccharine	1	1	1	1	1	1
Total	150	150	150	150	150	150

1. Precompression parameters:

Precompression parameters Sumatriptan mucoadhesive granules F₁- F₆.

F. No.	Bulk density (gm/cc)	Tapped density (gm/cc)	Angle of repose	Carr's index	Hausner's ratio
F ₁	0.288±0.05	0.326±0.09	18.46±0.15	11.65	1.13
F ₂	0.269±0.09	0.353±0.10	25.40±0.17	23.79	1.31
F ₃	0.274±0.04	0.344±0.08	21.35±0.11	20.34	1.25
F ₄	0.292±0.06	0.358±0.05	21.46±0.14	18.44	1.23
F ₅	0.258±0.10	0.320±0.08	22.14±0.09	19.38	1.24
F ₆	0.270±0.11	0.322±0.06	20.25±0.11	16.15	1.19

All values are expressed as average± SD; (n=3).

Post compression parameters:

Evaluation of post-compression parameters of Sumatriptan mucoadhesive matrix tablets F₁- F₆.

F. No.	Average hardness (kg/cm ²)	Average Weight Variation (mg)	Average friability (% w/w)	Average thickness (mm)	Content uniformity (%)	Bioadhesive strength (N)
F ₁	4.49±0.5	151±2.54	0.52±0.03	3.31±0.16	99.63±1.4	0.225±0.006
F ₂	4.40±0.6	150±2.24	0.48±0.06	3.36±0.12	98.22±1.8	0.188±0.004
F ₃	4.58±0.4	149±2.51	0.41±0.04	3.38±0.15	102.6±1.4	0.257±0.006
F ₄	4.56±0.3	148±2.42	0.54±0.06	3.32±0.12	99.18±1.4	0.229±0.003
F ₅	4.68±0.6	150±2.52	0.39±0.07	3.38±0.09	98.46±1.5	0.252±0.002
F ₆	4.76±0.4	152±2.62	0.42±0.04	3.39±0.10	99.61±1.2	0.273±0.006

All values are expressed as average± SD; (n=3).

Swelling study was performed on all the formulations (SMF₁ to SMF₁₂) for 10 hours. The formulation that contains HPMC K4M, and guar gum showed higher swelling indices due to higher hydrophilicity and more water uptake of the polymers. But reverse is observed with the formulations containing higher percentage of ethyl cellulose as it is a hydrophobic polymer.

Swelling studies of Sumatriptan mucoadhesive matrix tablets.

Time (Hrs)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆
1	12	10	14	11	8	11
2	17	18	25	19	16	16
3	28	34	36	26	27	27
4	35	45	47	34	38	36
5	49	59	58	46	46	45
6	61	74	72	57	58	57
7	76	91	89	74	72	73
8	92	-	102	88	87	90
9	108	-	115	102	101	105
10	125	-	-	117	118	122

In order to optimise the *in vitro* drug release along with bioadhesive force, different hydrophilic matrix polymers *viz.*, HPMC K4M, guar gum and hydrophobic matrix polymer *viz.*, ethyl cellulose were used for 6 different formulations of Sumatriptan mucoadhesive matrix tablets. In these studies HPMCK4M was usually used for sustained release effect with bioadhesive strength to some extent. It was observed that using hydrophilic polymer alone caused initial burst release because drug is hydrophilic in nature and maximum release upto 8 to 9 hour. So one more hydrophobic polymer *i.e* ethyl cellulose was added to reduce the initial burst release and also it had remarkable bioadhesive strength. Among all the formulations, SMF₆ could be considered as optimised formulation as the initial release was 11% and maximum release upto 10 hours and had remarkable bioadhesive strength that may be adequate criteria for bioadhesive formulation.

Cumulative % *in-vitro* drug release studies of Sumatriptan mucoadhesive tablet formulations SMF₁ – SMF₆.

Time (Hrs)	F ₁	F ₂	F ₃	F ₄	F ₅	F ₆	Marketed Sumatriptan SR formulation
1	9.12	18.28	7.48	10.83	12.4	11.38	11.21
2	16.45	29.42	16.65	18.72	19.52	18.46	19.53
3	28.52	41.73	24.82	27.61	30.69	29.71	30.62
4	37.67	54.64	35.47	39.38	45.68	36.48	39.16
5	45.65	65.75	44.82	48.41	59.48	45.76	48.58
6	58.81	78.49	57.61	60.2	71.54	57.83	61.44
7	64.47	89.62	65.72	68.39	80.85	69.91	68.29
8	76.62	99.71	76.69	79.15	88.49	76.3	79.43
9	84.53	-	86.34	89.36	96.52	89.44	87.69
10	91.21	-	94.56	99.42	99.76	99.09	96.83
11	99.26	-	99.16	-	-	-	99.41
12	-	-	-	-	-	-	-

The *in vitro* dissolution data of optimised formulation SMF₆ were fitted in different kinetic models viz. zero order, first order, Higuchi and Korse-Meyer Peppas's kinetic model equation and the graphs were plotted. The zero-order plots were found to be fairly linear as indicated by their highest regression values. The release exponent 'n' for optimised formulation SMF₆ was found to be 0.95 ($0.5 < n < 1$), which appears to indicate a coupling of the diffusion and erosion mechanism so-called anomalous diffusion. So in present study *in vitro* drug release kinetic of optimised formulation of Sumatriptan mucoadhesive matrix tablets followed zero order release kinetic models and drug release mechanism is anomalous diffusion coupled with erosion

In-vitro drug release kinetic studies of optimised formulation (SMF₆).

Time (Hour)	% CDR	% ARR	Log % ARR	Log % CDR	\sqrt{t}	Log t
0	0	0	2	0	0	0
1	11.38	88.62	1.95	1.06	1	0
2	18.46	81.54	1.91	1.27	1.414	0.30
3	29.71	70.29	1.85	1.47	1.732	0.48
4	36.48	63.58	1.80	1.56	2	0.60
5	45.76	54.24	1.73	1.66	2.236	0.69
6	57.83	42.17	1.63	1.76	2.449	0.78
7	69.91	30.09	1.48	1.84	2.646	0.85
8	76.30	23.7	1.37	1.88	2.828	0.90
9	89.44	10.56	1.03	1.95	3	0.95
10	99.09	0.91	-0.04	1.99	3.162	1

Table 5: Regression values of *in-vitro* release kinetic study optimized Sumatriptan mucoadhesive tablet (SMF₆).

Formulation	R ² value of Zero order	R ² value of 1 st order	R ² value of Higuchi model	R ² value of Peppas's model	'n' value of Peppas's model
SMF ₆	0.997	0.891	0.963	0.993	0.957

DSC thermogram of pure drug Sumatriptan Succinate

DSC thermogram of Sumatriptan Mucoadhesive tablet (SMF12)

CONCLUSION

In the present work Sumatriptan buccal mucoadhesive matrix tablet were successfully developed. The major challenge in this work was to study the effect of various low density polymers on *in vitro* release rate of buccal mucoadhesive of Sumatriptan with adequate bioadhesive force for prolonging the drug residence time in buccal mucosa. The mucoadhesive and *in vitro* drug release effect of different types of low density matrix forming polymers HPMC K4M, Guar gum and Ethyl cellulose were studied. The main objective of using hydrophobic polymer ethyl cellulose with HPMC was to prevent the burst release effect the hydrophilic drug under study with hydrophilic polymer like HPMC, guar gum and it is having good bioadhesive nature which was successfully developed. Formulation SMFF₆ that contained of all the three polymers i.e. HPMC K4M, guar gum and ethyl cellulose showed sustained drug release for 10 hour (99%) and had adequate bioadhesive strength, emerged as optimised formulation. Increase in proportion of hydrophilic polymer caused initial burst release effect. To overcome that effect hydrophobic polymer ethyl cellulose were added. Kinetic of *in vitro* drug release of optimized formulation SMF₆ found to be zero order having drug release mechanism as anomalous diffusion coupled with erosion. FTIR studies revealed that there is no chemical interaction between drug and polymers. DSC studies proved that no thermal interaction between the drug Sumatriptan and polymer used in the present studies. Thus from the results of the current study clearly indicate, a promising potential of the Sumatriptan buccal mucoadhesive system as an alternative to the conventional dosage form as it enhance bioavailability of the Sumatriptan by bypassing the first pass metabolism and by producing sustained release effect for sustainable migraine. However, further clinical studies are needed to assess the utility of this system for patients suffering from migraine.

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